

Supporting large scale XAS data processing, analysis, and FAIR publishing with scientific workflows

Presenter: Abraham Nieva de la Hidalga

Abraham Nieva de la Hidalga, Leandro Liborio, Patrick Austin, Hector Perez Ponce, Slava Tykhonov, Deidre Lungley, Stephen Richard, Markus Kubin, Heike Görzig, Simon Hodson, Arofan Gregory, Rolf Krahl, Matti Heikkurinen, Richard Catlow.

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Support XAS processing for larger datasets

Goal:

- Facilitate processing of large XAS datasets aligned with FAIR principles

Problem:

- Interactive processing of large datasets and preservation of metadata (FAIR requirement) is slow and error prone

Proposal:

- Tools that automate metadata collection during processing and analysis producing publish ready FAIR data

Larger XAS datasets and more complex analyses

Brighter

More coherent

Faster

- Large scale facilities evolve
- Experiments produce larger and more complex datasets
- Data needs to be processed, analysed, and preserved
- Challenging to support reproducibility and reuse

3rd and 4th Generation Beamlines

Preserving metadata is a big challenge

Processing times for large XAS datasets

3,790 XAS spectra

Read Raw Data

Process, Normalise, Re-bin, Data

FEFF fit of Crystal Paths to EXAFS Data

Interactive Manual methods

 Novice: ~63 Days
 Expert: ~26 Days

Command Line, No UI

Demeter Script: ~23 Hours

Larch Script: ~103 Hours

NextFlow Workflow: ~7 Hours

Web Based Customisable UI

Galaxy Workflow: ~7 Hours

Galaxy XAS Tools

Larch

Data Analysis Tools for X-ray Spectroscopy

Scientific
Computing
Department

- Python, X-Ray Larch, Galaxy
- Web Based interface
- No setup required
- Medium/Large scale XAS analyses (in-situ or operando)

Activity Bar

Activity Panel

Viewing Panel

History

The screenshot displays the Galaxy materialsGalaxy interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Data', 'Admin', 'Help', 'User', and a home icon, with a memory usage indicator of 'Using 717.4 MB'. The interface is divided into four main vertical panels:

- Activity Bar (left):** Contains navigation icons for Upload, Tools, Workflows, Workflow Invocations, Visualization, Histories, History Multiview, Datasets, Pages, Settings, and Admin.
- Activity Panel (middle-left):** Lists various tools categorized by function: Get Data (MUONS, MuSpinSim, Find Muon Stopping Sites, Other Muon Tools), XAS (Larch Select Paths, Larch Plot, Larch Athena, Larch Artemis), Larch FEF, Larch LCF, Larch Criteria Report, OTHER TOOLS (File Conversion, Collection Operations), and WORKFLOWS (All workflows).
- Viewing Panel (middle-right):** Shows the configuration for the 'Larch Athena' tool. The description is 'generate Athena projects from XAFS data (Galaxy Version 0.9.80+galaxy1)'. The tool is currently set to 'True'. Parameters include: 'kmin' (Minimum k value), 'kmax' (Maximum k value), 'kweight' (Exponent for weighting spectra), 'dk' (Tapering parameter), 'window' (Fourier Transform window type), and 'Plot graphs' (options for Select/Deselect all, Pre/post edge fitting, Flattened x_μ, and Derivative of x_μ). There is also a 'Zip outputs' toggle set to 'No'. A 'Run Tool' button is visible at the bottom.
- History Panel (right):** Lists a series of completed jobs, such as 'Paper 1: XANES, LCF, EXAFS', '104: ChiKR plot on data 92, data 91, and others', '103: RMR plot on data 92, data 91, and others', etc., with icons for viewing and deleting each entry.

7 Galaxy Tools

Galaxy materialsGalaxy

Workflow Visualize Data Admin Help Users Using 717.4 MB

Tools

search tools

Get Data

MUONS

MuSpinSim

Find Muon Stopping Sites

Other Muon Tools

XAS

- Larch Select Paths** select FEFF paths for XAFS data
- Larch Plot** plot Athena projects
- Larch Athena** generate Athena projects from XAFS data
- Larch Artemis** generate Artemis projects from XAFS data
- Larch FEFF** generate FEFF paths from XAFS data
- Larch LCF** perform linear combination fit on XAS data
- Larch Criteria Report** generate reports on Artemis fitting from XAFS data

OTHER TOOLS

File Conversion

Collection Operations

WORKFLOWS

All workflows

Larch Athena
generate Athena projects from XAFS data
(Galaxy Version 0.9.8.0+galaxy1)

True
If set, will (re)perform forward Fourier Transform

kmin - optional

Minimum k value. (kmin)

kmax - optional

Maximum k value. (kmax)

kweight - optional

Exponent for weighting spectra by raising to the power of

dk - optional

Tapering parameter for Fourier Transform

window - optional

Nothing selected

Fourier Transform window type. (window)

Plot graphs - optional

Select / Deselect all

Pre/post edge fitting

Flattened $x\mu$

Derivative of $x\mu$

Zip outputs

No

XAS

- Larch Artemis** generate Artemis projects from XAFS data
- Larch Athena** generate Athena projects from XAFS data
- Larch Criteria Report** generate reports on Artemis fitting from XAFS data
- Larch FEFF** generate FEFF paths from XAFS data
- Larch LCF** perform linear combination fit on XAS data
- Larch Plot** plot Athena projects
- Larch Select Paths** select FEFF paths for XAFS data

a 91, and others

95: ChiKR plot on data 92, data 91, and others

Types of analyses supported

Normal plot of aligned samples

Compare fit components

Formation of components in time

Highlight regions in a catalytic surface

Compare standard to samples

Sample behaviour in time

Linear Combination Fit of different samples

Examples taken from actual published papers (with published data)
from UK Catalysis Hub colleagues

Combining tools into a workflow

- Enables reproducibility
- Automated execution over larger datasets
- Packaged results as RO-Crates

RO-Crates are FAIR Digital Objects

Input data, parameters, variables, intermediate data, and results (reports and images)

Full provenance

Workflow in open formats

Examples:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rexas>

FeS2 RO-Crate

zenodo

Search records...

Communities

My dashboard

a_nieva@...

Reproducible XAFS Analyses

Published October 24, 2024 | Version v1

Dataset

Open

Manage

Edit

New version

Share

Reproducing the FeS2 Example from the Demeter Tutorials

Nieva de la Hidalga, Abraham (Producer)^{1,2}

Show affiliations

These files are provided to complement the learning materials for managing RO-Crates in Galaxy.

The files included are:

- A crystal structure file for performing a feff fit (1564889.cif).
- A XAS spectra file to process and analyse (fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu).
- A Galaxy workflow file to perform the process and analysis (Galaxy-Workflow-FeS2_Analysis.ga)
- A Galaxy RO-Crate file which can be restored to see the processing and analysis directly.

The workflow and RO-Crate reproduce the EXAFS fitting example for athena and artemis as described by [Bruce Ravel](#). Instead of using the FeS2.inp file in the original example, the workflow uses a crystal structure file ([1564889.cif](#)) from the Crystallography Open Database (COD).

This RO is published as part of the research data submitted for the paper **Facilitating Reproducibility in Catalysis Research with Managed Workflows and RO-Crates: A Galaxy Case Study**, ChemCatChem, DOI: 10.1002/cctc.202401676.

Notes (English)

These data are used in the tutorials:

- [Import RO-Crate](#)
- [Import Workflow](#)
- Reproducible results: Create RO-Crate and Export Workflow

Recommended Server to follow tutorial: Materials Galaxy (<https://materialsgalaxy.stfc.ac.uk/>)

221
VIEWES

191
DOWNLOADS

Show more details

Versions

Version v1

Oct 24, 2024

10.5281/zenodo.13987511

Cite all versions? You can cite all versions by using the DOI [10.5281/zenodo.13987510](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987510). This DOI represents all versions, and will always resolve to the latest one. [Read more](#).

External resources

Indexed in

OpenAIRE

How FAIR

Published RO Crate

The screenshot shows a Zenodo repository page for a dataset titled "Reproducing the FeS2 Example from the Demeter Tutorials". The page includes a search bar, user profile, and navigation links. The main content area features a title, author information (Néve de la Hédaga, Abraham (Producer)), and a description of the dataset. It lists included files: a crystal structure file, XAS spectra, a Galaxy workflow, and a Galaxy RO-Crate file. A "Notes" section provides instructions on how to use the workflow and RO-Crate. The right sidebar shows management options (Edit, New version, Share), statistics (221 views, 191 downloads), and version information (Version v1, 10.5291/zenodo.13967511, Oct 24, 2024).

Can be restored to Galaxy and inspected

Workflow

Workflow execution

The screenshot shows the execution details of the "FeS2 Analysis from RO-Crate" workflow. The main panel displays a "New Graph" view of the workflow steps, including "3: Larch Athena", "4: Larch FEFF", and "5: Larch Select Paths". A "Workflow Details" panel on the right lists the steps and their outputs, such as "Workflow Details", "3: feo2_rft1_mmr92.xmu", "3: 1964869.cif", "3: Athena project file", "3: FEFF paths file", "3: GDS parameters file", "3: SF parameters file", "3: fit_report_FeS2 (left)", "3: mmr_FeS2 (png)", and "3: chkr_FeS2 (png)". A "History" panel on the far right shows a list of dataset versions with their respective IDs and checkmarks indicating successful execution.

Processing details

Dataset History

FeS2 Workflow

FeS2 RO-Crate data

No.	Activity	Tool	Dataset	Inputs
0	fetch data from history	DATA_FETCH	1564889.cif	None
1	calculate FEFF paths from crystal	larch_feff	CSV summary of 1564889.cif	1564889.cif
2	calculate FEFF paths from crystal	larch_feff	FEFF input of 1564889.cif	1564889.cif
3	calculate FEFF paths from crystal	larch_feff	FEFF paths of 1564889.cif	1564889.cif
4	process and normalise XAS	larch_athena	FeS2_athena	fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu
5	process and normalise XAS	larch_athena	FeS2_plot	fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu
6	FEFF fit of XAS	larch_athena	chikr_FeS2	FeS2_athena, FEFF paths of 1564889.cif, fes2_g...
7	select FEFF paths	larch_select_paths	fes2_gds	CSV summary of 1564889.cif, FEFF paths of 1564...
8	fetch data from history	DATA_FETCH	fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu	None
9	select FEFF paths	larch_select_paths	fes2_sp	CSV summary of 1564889.cif, FEFF paths of 1564...
10	FEFF fit of XAS	larch_athena	fit_report_FeS2	FeS2_athena, FEFF paths of 1564889.cif, fes2_g...
11	FEFF fit of XAS	larch_athena	rnr_FeS2	FeS2_athena, FEFF paths of 1564889.cif, fes2_g...

XAS .xmu file (raw data)

No.	Property	Value
0	rdf:type	prov:Entity
1	rdf:type	cdifprov:Dataset
2	dcterms:format	text/plain
3	dcterms:description	uploaded txt file
4	schema1:id	datasets/fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu_df0bac1ee137448a.txt
5	skos:prefLabel	fes2_rt01_mar02.xmu
6	prov:wasGeneratedBy	fetch data from history
7	prov:wasAttributedTo	DATA_FETCH
8	prov:wasAttributedTo	larch_athena
9	dcterms:subject	panet:PaNET01196

```

#%name: FeS2 powder Room Temperature
#%atom: FeS2
#%edge: K
#%xtal: FeS2.inp
#%prep: powder on tape, 4 layers
#%ref: none
#%misc: Energy drive values recorded (encoder used)
#%det: I0=N2 15cm; I1=N2 15cm
#%temp: Room Temperature
#%beam: GSECARS 13BM, vert slits = 2mm (at 45m)
#%mono: Si(111) unfocussed, detuned 50%
#%date: Sat Mar 16 15:13:22 2002
#%cols: 348 E XMU I0
#-----
# energy XMU I0
6911.8277 0.80926541 272002.00
6916.9236 0.80418730 270032.00
6921.7638 0.79959074 268827.00
6926.8750 0.79459529 267514.00
6931.7907 0.79004613 255214.00
6962.0000 0.78791063 305150.00
6972.0000 0.77475191 306445.00
6982.0000 0.76169076 306446.00

```


Working on the further improvement of the tools

XDI conversion requires simple mappings
 Nxxas is more complex (binary).
 HZB's NeXus Converter, supports creating
 nexus application files using templates (no
 hardcoding)

Use CODATA's CDIF mapping tools to
 generate on outputs to obtain discovery
 metadata

Even FAIRer RO-Crates

Read Galaxy RO-Crate

Exported workflow run form Galaxy

Read Context Metadata

Data type
Name
Origin
Sample
Element

Further Processing

Plotting
Alternative processing

Read Provenance information

Processing stages
Parameters
Input data
Output data

Recover dataset

In galaxy or unpacked it and use it in other environments

Extend the provenance chain

Metadata about further processing of signals

Improved Discovery, Reuse, Interoperability

- XAS Galaxy tools and RO-Crates enable reproducibility and reuse
- RO-Crate structure data and make it available outside Galaxy
- CDIF-4-XAS enhances the tools and RO-Crates introducing the use of community accepted standard

Available from
September 2026

XAS Galaxy Tools

FAIR data is AI ready data

10.1016/j.envsoft.2020.104753 and https://jhudatascience.org/Reproducibility_in_Cancer_Informatics

Try it now

<https://materials-galaxy.stfc.ac.uk>

<https://usegalaxy.eu>

The screenshot shows the Materials Galaxy web interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Galaxy materialsGalaxy', a home icon, and menu items for 'Workflow', 'Visualize', 'Shared Data', 'Help', 'User', and a notification bell. The right side of the header shows 'Using 3.4 MB'.

Tools Panel (Left): Features a search bar for tools, an 'Upload Data' button, and categorized tool lists:

- Get Data**
- SPIN DYNAMICS**: MuSpinSim
- FIND MUON STOPPING SITES**: UEP Method, Other Methods
- OTHER TOOLS**: PyMuonSuite, File Conversion, Collection Operations
- XAS**
- WORKFLOWS**: All workflows

Main Content Area:

- Welcome to Materials Galaxy!**: Introduction text stating that Materials Galaxy provides access to tools for tackling computational challenges in muon spectroscopy and X-ray absorption spectroscopy. It mentions the Galaxy framework and its flexibility.
- New to Materials Galaxy?**: Offers an interactive tour with buttons for 'Galaxy UI', 'History', and 'Scratchbook'. It also lists tutorials: 'Galaxy 101 for everyone', 'Finding muon stopping sites with PyMuonSuite', and 'Modelling spin dynamics with MuSpinSim (coming soon)'.
- Reproducibility & Transparency**: Explains that history is the foundation of reproducibility and transparency, capturing inputs, parameters, and tool versions.
- Galaxy provides also a powerful workflow system.** Describes how workflows can be created by extraction from histories or from scratch, and are shareable with everyone.
- Contact Us**: A link at the bottom of the main content area.

History Panel (Right): Shows a search bar for datasets and a list of workflow steps for 'EXAFS_test' (1.13 MB, 26 items):

- 26: ChiKR plot on data 10, data 9, and others
- 25: RMR plot on data 10, data 9, and others
- 24: Fit report on data 10, data 9, and others
- 23: Merged directories from data 5 and data 6
- 22: FEFF input of 1564889.cif
- 21: FEFF paths of 1564889.cif
- 20: CSV summary of 1564889.cif
- 19: Plot of data 1

Published reusable XAS datasets

- 10 Examples
- Packages relevant data and metadata in RO-Crate format
- Streamlined publication
- Facilitate data sharing, reproducibility, and provenance tracking.
- Can be imported to Galaxy for verification and testing.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rexas>

<https://doi.org/10.1002/cctc.202401676>

Tutorials

PSDI
Science and Technology Facilities Council
CatalysisHub
Galaxy PROJECT

Galaxy RO Crates

PSDI Minitutorials

- Research Object Crate
- Starting with RO-Crates
- Further Learning

Research Object Crate

A Galaxy RO-Crate is a digital object intended to preserve data, configurations and parameters; ensure the accurate reproduction of results; and facilitate publishing of supporting data for research works (papers, books, theses).

RO-Crates are not an exclusive Galaxy product, they are used in other contexts as an open alternative to creating FAIR Digital Objects for Research.

```
graph TD; Galaxy[Galaxy XAS TOOLS] --> Create[Create Workflow]; Import[Import Workflow]; ImportRO[Import RO-Crate]; Run[Run Workflow]; Inspect[Inspect Results]; Export[Export RO-Crate]; Publish[Publish RO-Crate]; Create --> Run; Import --> Run; ImportRO --> Run; Run --> Inspect; Inspect --> Export; Export --> Publish; Publish --> ImportRO; Publish --> Import; Publish --> Create;
```

The diagram illustrates the RO-Crate Lifecycle in the Galaxy environment, showing its direct relation to workflows and their executions. The cycle begins with the creation or import of a workflow. Next, the workflow is invoked, processing data to produce results. Then, results are inspected to ensure all outputs are correct. Following this, the workflow invocation is exported as an RO-Crate, preserving inputs, parameters, intermediate, and final results. Finally, the RO-Crate is published.

- Importing and Running a workflow
- Creating an RO-Crate
- Importing an RO-Crate

https://xerte.cardiff.ac.uk/play_22679

PSDI & Royce Materials Data Summit

What We Provide ▾ Cross Data Search ▾ Guidance ▾ Community ▾ About PSDI ▾

< [Back to all Events](#)

29-31 July 2026
Manchester, UK

PSDI & Royce Materials Data Summit

- Dates:** 29th -31st July 2026
- Location:** Nancy Rothwell Building, University of Manchester, Manchester, M13 9PL
- Organised by:** The Henry Royce Institute & the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure

Overview

The [Henry Royce Institute](#) and the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) are pleased to announce the PSDI & Royce Materials Data Summit, which will be held from 29th to 31st July 2026 at the University of Manchester.

Date
29th July 2026 - 31st July 2026

Time
All Day Event

https://www.psd.ac.uk/event/psdi_royce_materials_data_summit/

 UKRI Science and Technology Facilities Council

Scientific Computing Department

 Leandro Liborio

 Patrick Austin

 Subindev Devasam

 Alex Belozarov

 Tom Underwood

 diamond

 Nitya Raman

 CatalysisHub

 CARDIFF UNIVERSITY
PRIFYSGOL CAERDYDD

 Abraham Nieva

 C.R.A. Catlow

 Martin Wilding

 UKRI

Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council

PSDI-EP SRC: EP/X032701/1, EP/X032663/1, EP/W032252/1

OSCARS

Open Science Clusters' Action
for Research & Society

Simon Hodson (PI)

Arofan Gregory

Matti Heikkurinen

Slava Tykhonov

Stephen Richard

University
of Essex

UK Data Service

Deidre Lungley

Science and
Technology
Facilities Council

Leandro Liborio

Patrick Austin

PSDI
PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Abraham Nieva

C.R.A. Catlow

Helmholtz
Zentrum Berlin

Heike Görzig

Rolf Krahl

Markus Kubin

Hector Perez Ponce

Funded by
the European Union

OSCARS EU-ERI 101129751

Engineering and
Physical Sciences
Research Council

PSDI-EP SRC: EP/X032701/1,
EP/X032663/1, EP/W032252/1

CatalysisHub

BEALE

DRIVAS

DECAROLIS

PARLETT

WELLS

Thank you

Figure 28. Fitting of Asian elephant to XAS spectra of MoOx/Al₂O₃ at 500 °C

Note: Elephant signal generated by copilot

Observe that Chiang Mai is a good fit for the XAFS 2026 conference

Supplementary Slides

- Slides below only to be used if time permits
respond questions
- Can also be used to ~~further confuse attendants~~
- Increase slide count

A piece in a larger puzzle

- Develop a FAIR-by-design approach for creating FAIR digital objects
- Create the CDIF4EOSC Playbook to enable FAIR integration aligned with EOSC data management practices

<https://www.cdif4eosc.eu>

Tools and packages used

- Galaxy: Create tools and workflows for processing XAS data
<https://materials galaxy.stfc.ac.uk/> and <https://usegalaxy.eu/>
- X-Ray Larch: process and analyse XAS data
<https://xraypy.github.io/xraylarch/>
- NeXusCreator: create and transform NeXus files using application definitions
<https://pypi.org/project/nexuscreator/>
- CDIF4XAS mapper: extract CDIF profiles from XDI and NeXus files
<https://github.com/codata/cdi-xas>
- Tested:
 - Updating RO Crate:
 - Python rocrate: <https://pypi.org/project/rocrate/>
 - NOVACrate: <https://novacrate.datamanager.kit.edu/>
 - Publishing RO Crate
 - deploy2zenodo/deploy2invenio for publishing: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19653992>
 - Python rocrate-inveniordm <https://pypi.org/project/rocrate-inveniordm/>

Current status

- XAS Tools for processing and analysis
 - Tested on datasets from published work
 - Reproduction of results
 - Processing of large datasets
- CDIF-4-XAS tools
 - Consume and Produce Nexus and XDI data
 - Create CDIF profile for rapid identification and interoperability of data
- RO-Crate prepublishing processing
 - Add provenance and context metadata to Galaxy RO-Crates
- Scripts for Publishing RO-Crates
 - Facilitate publishing to Invenio RDM (Zenodo)

Published and ready for use

Available from September 2026

Plotting data

```
# XDI/1.0 Athena/0.9.26
# Element.edge: K
# Element.symbol: Fe
# Column.1: energy eV
# Column.2: norm
# Column.3: rbgk
# Column.4: flat
# Column.5: fbgk
# Column.6: ndr
# Column.7: msec
# Athena.e0: 7117
# Athena.eshift: 0
# Athena.rbgk: 1.0
# Athena.importance: 1
# Athena.standard: None
# Athena.bkg_weight: 2
# Athena.edge_step: 0.7600727
# Athena.flat_step: no
# Athena.pre_edge_range: -150.000 -30.000
# Athena.pre_edge_line: 9.340137 - 0.00122868 * E
# Athena.normalization_range: 150.000 752.247
# Athena.post_edge_polynomial: 34.535916 - 0.00779179 * E + 4.35533395e-007 * E^2 + 0 * E^3
# Athena.spline_range_energy: 0.000 851.225
# Athena.clamp: 0 24
# Athena.spline_range_k: 0.000 14.956
# Athena.k_weight: 2
# Athena.window: hanning
# Athena.phase_correction: no
# Athena.k_range: 3.000 12.956
# Athena.dk: 1
# Athena.r_range: 1 3
# Athena.dr: 0.0
# Athena.window: hanning
# Athena.plot_multiplier: 1
# Athena.y_offset: 0
# ///
# -----
# e      norm      rbgk      flat      fbgk      ndr      msec
6916.9236 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 0.38545276E-03 0.58917883E-05
6916.9236 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 0.33547631E-03 0.43197540E-05
6916.9236 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 -0.49069918E-01 0.38545276E-03 0.58917883E-05
```


For instance: just extracting the Normalised data for plotting

Domain specific metadata

The image shows a code editor window displaying JSON metadata for a dataset. The JSON structure is as follows:

```
1 {
2   "@context": {
3     "schema": "https://schema.org/",
4     "cif": "https://www.iucr.org/resources/cif",
5     "goldbook": "https://goldbook.iupac.org/",
6     "temperatureRange": ...,
10    "temperatureScale": ...,
14    "rampRate": ...,
18    "gasComposition": ...,
22    "Facility": ...,
27    "Beamline": ...,
33    "Catalyst": ...,
39    "Support": ...,
45    "ChemicalSubstance": ...
51  },
52  "datasets": [
53    {
54      "@type": "Dataset",
55      "name": "LaMnO3 catalytic behaviour",
56      "url": "https://zenodo.org/records/14013574",
57      "description": "<p>Galaxy RO Crate object containing the workflow and data with the reprodu
58      "pids": {
```

Annotations in the image include:

- A red box with the text **schema.org** pointing to the `"schema"` field in the `@context` object.
- A logo for **IUCr** (International Union of Crystallography) pointing to the `"cif"` field.
- A logo for **IUPAC** (International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry) pointing to the `"goldbook"` field.

The code editor interface includes a menu bar (File, Edit, View, Git, Project, Debug, Test, Analyze, Tools, Extensions, Window, Help), a search bar, and a status bar at the bottom showing "Ready" and "Select Repository".

schema.org

Roadmap for transforming heterogeneous catalysis with artificial intelligence

Received: 11 July 2025

Accepted: 6 January 2026

Published online: 16 February 2026

 Check for updates

Hongliang Xin¹✉, John R. Kitchin²✉, Núria López³✉, Neil M. Schweitzer⁴✉, Nongnuch Artrith⁵, Fanglin Che⁶, Lars C. Grabow⁷, G. T. Kasun Kalhara Gunasooriya⁸, Heather J. Kulik⁹, Teodoro Laino^{10,11}, Hao Li¹², Suljo Linic¹³, Andrew J. Medford¹⁴, Randall J. Meyer¹⁵, Jiayu Peng¹⁶, Cory Phillips¹⁷, Jin Qian¹⁸, Long Qi¹⁹, Wendy J. Shaw²⁰, Zachary W. Ulissi²¹, Siwen Wang²² & Xiaonan Wang²³

Artificial intelligence (AI) is poised to transform heterogeneous catalysis, opening avenues for catalytic materials discovery. By uncovering intricate patterns in high-dimensional data, AI has been reshaping our pursuit of sustainable catalytic processes across the energy, environmental and chemical sectors. This promise, however, hinges on overcoming fundamental barriers, including limitations in data availability and quality, challenges in the generalizability and interpretability of data-augmented decisions, and the persistent gap between *in silico* predictions and experiments. Here we outline a forward-looking roadmap for deeply integrating AI into heterogeneous catalysis with an AI-ready data ecosystem, multimodal foundation models, and ultimately autonomous laboratories to accelerate the development of next-generation catalytic technologies via AI-empowered human-machine collaboration.

